

ECOBULK

The furniture in this room is part of the EcoBulk project. We aim to make composite materials more sustainable and circular.

The furniture has been designed with standardised modular parts, allowing easy repair and reuse. In addition, the pressed wood does not use traditional glues that make their recycling complex and hazardous for operators.

Let us hear from you! Follow the short link or QR code below to give us feedback and get more info.

[Short link here]

Did you know?

10 million tonnes of furniture are discarded by businesses and consumers in the EU each year, the majority of which is destined for either landfill or incineration

